

A Study of the Relationship Between Performance and Motivation in Informal Trade (A Case of Grocery Shops in Selected Markets in Lusaka District of Zambia)

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Some traders do succeed while others fail and others remain on the same level, or even fail, given that all players operate in the same business environment. Initiatives to reduce on informal trading and promote formalization of businesses are top on national agendas. **Aim of the study:** The study aims to identify those values that are being held by successful entrepreneurs in informal trade. **Methodology:** Sample size of 297 respondents were chosen from the centrally placed six markets in Lusaka district. The study employs a mixed method design which hinges on correlation of motivation with performance. Annual sales, rather than monthly are chosen, for annual figures reflect a period long enough to gather reliable information for purposes of analysis. Increase in sales has been used as a measure of growth. A questionnaire is the main instrument of research. **Findings:** There is a strong positive correlation ($r=0.82$) between Annual sales and 'other' motivation among informal traders. **Discussion:** A blend of motivational values enhances performance among informal trader. **Conclusion:** Government should package a blend of motivational influences and replicate such to make other traders grow and transition into formal businesses.

Keywords: Performance; Motivation; Grocery shops; Lusaka district; Zambia.

1.0. Introduction

This research study investigates key motivational force that motivates informal traders. The focus is on grocery traders. The background is that some traders do succeed while others fail and others remain on the same level. The questions being (a) why is it so given that the traders operate in almost about the same business environment.? (b) Why is it that some traders succeed while their counterparts fail or lag behind? In both cases (the successful traders and the unsuccessful) there are driven by largely the profit motive. This study turns to motivation as an ingredient or a motivating force to improved performance among the traders. Motivation is categorised as being intrinsic, extrinsic or 'other' (which includes a hybrid of intrinsic and extrinsic and a conducive environment provided by authorities). The aim is to identify those values that are being held by successful entrepreneurs (in informal trade) so that such are properly packed by agents of government to be replicated to other areas in order to help small business grow only to become formal businesses and this would lead to a drop in informality of informal trade. Informal trade does not meaningfully contribute to a nation's Gross Domestic Product which would translate into more revenue and more development for a nation. So the aim of a government would be to keep shrinking the size of this sector by way of helping business to grow. Also informal businesses are hard to supervise, monitor and policy. Initiatives to reduce on informal trading and promote formalization of businesses are top on national agendas.

1.1. Research Hypothesis

1.1.1. Hypothesis 1

Alternative hypothesis 1

Sales growth for an informal trader correlates with intrinsic motivation S varies as $M_{Intrinsic}$

Null hypothesis 1

Sales growth among informal traders does not correlate to Intrinsic motivation.

$$\frac{S}{M_{intrinsic}} \neq K$$

1.1.2. Hypothesis 2

Alternative hypothesis 2

Sales growth for an informal trader correlates with Extrinsic motivation *S varies as $M_{Extrinsic}$*

Null hypothesis 2

Sales growth or an informal business does not correlate with extrinsic motivation.

$$\frac{S}{M_{Extrinsic}} \neq K$$

1.1.3. Hypothesis 3

Alternative hypothesis 3

Sales growth for an informal trader correlates with other forms of motivation *S varies as M_{Other}*

Null hypothesis 3

$$\frac{S}{M_{Other}} \neq K \quad \text{Where } S = \text{Annual Sales}; M = \text{Motivation, Subscript} = \text{type of } M$$

1.2. Scope of the Study

The study is restricted to informal traders in selected markets of Lusaka district. The market are the main markets that are at the end or beginning of bus routes. The chosen markets represent the character of informal trade across the country, with markets at the extreme end of a road, where there is about a bus station and other informal structures around the market and along the roads (Phiri & Kabaso, 2012).

2.0. Theoretical Considerations

2.1. Characterizing grocery trade

A grocery store stocks primarily food items with a smaller addition of non-food items that includes body lotions, cosmetics, hardware, electronic goods and linen. The primary stocked items are food and non-food items for household use, rather around the issue of food and human consumption. Most shops, in Lusaka, are owner-operated and managed and trade as sole-traders who may not have a registered business name but with only a trading license from a local municipality (Phiri & Kabaso, 2012).

Space is limited for the informal grocery operator just like capital and investment. Yet the shop business is said to be profitable and with sustainable sales volumes given that consumption of goods including food characterizes much of human activities and needs. So an informal trader is assured of trading or business. Challenge in grocery business is intense competition (given the existence of many shops trading in similar or same items within a defined area. The other challenge is that grocery trade is characterized by low profit margins, high transport costs and also

usually, low-income clientele. The other challenge is limited trading space with a floor area of nine square metre being common (Masaka, 2022).

2.2. Informal sector business

The informal sector comprises the whole group that includes micro-enterprises, small businesses, trading concerns, traders, marketers, small manufacturing firms and establishments (who include welders, metal-fabricators, carpenters, blacksmiths, bakers) and hawkers, among the many categories that includes also tailors, radio-repair shop, hair dressers, small restaurants and hardware shops, motor vehicle repair shops (Phiri & Kabaso 2012).

An informal business is one that is neither taxed nor regulated by the Central Government (Isak & Mohamud, 2022). The informal sector is informal because formal arrangements, including laws and regulations are not sufficiently, applied observed, or applicable (ILO, 2000).

Regulation refers to the entire system of laws and procedures that controls or supervises the functioning, operation or well-being of a system (Umoeakafor, 2020). An illegal enterprise is one that trades, produces, distributes or is associated, prohibited or outlawed goods and service (Zabyelina & Van-Uhm, 2020). Growth refers to the whole process of 'growing big' and transforming into a fully-fledged formally regulated business (the key concept is 'transitioning to become a formal trader). An increase in the number of employees can indicate growth of an informal enterprise. Other indicators of growth are an *increase in turnover*, market share and level of investment, with turnover being the most common measure or indicator (Mahmutaj & Krasniqi, 2020). Informal trade is seen as a means of survival and employment for many people across the globe, both in the developed world or developing world (ILO, 2000).

Globally, two billion people take part in informal employment, with the accompanying risks and vulnerabilities. This translates into 60% of the global labour force and 90% of all small scale to medium enterprises and presents challenges on how to manage this growing but vulnerable sector (Etim & Daramola, 2020).

Lack of capital or finance, poor infrastructure (which include roads and telecommunications), poor training in business management, lack of mentorship, as well as high cost of doing business, are some of the common challenges facing informal traders in the developing world. Good record keeping practices, are other values which are lacking among many informal traders. Informality has been linked to poor economic performance, poor legal frameworks, lack of government policy, as well as insufficient or poor oversight on the part of government or its agents (ILO, 2000). Poor education, or low level of education, lack of sufficient capital, discrimination, poverty, high costs of compliance, among other factors, can also be cited as determinants of driving forces for informality (David et al, 2013)

3.0. Motivation

Motivation generally refers to initiatives that management puts in place to control the behaviour of employees. (Appleby, 1994). Motivation refers therefore to the whole set of packages, including conditions that drive employees to aspire to achieve and even to actually achieve set goes. In the sense of informal traders, motivation refers to those forces that inspire traders or business players to achieve set objectives and even to aspire for success in the midst of tough working conditions and a challenging business environment that characterise that sector.

Evanchevich, Gibson & Donnelly (1991) do show that most scholars on motivation, beginning with Abraham Maslow, to Fredrick Herzberg, to A'lderfer, to Mclelland; all to put one set of motivational forces or needs on one side against another set, depicting that motivational forces not only are they not uniform but can be differentiated and have different effect on different individuals. This characterisation of motivational forces to attest to the fact that motivation it is alright to segment motivational forces even for traders as intrinsic and extrinsic.

3.1. Intrinsic motivation

Intrinsic motivation is that type of motivation that comes from within an individual, motivated by the individual's desires and wants while extrinsic motivation is the type of motivation that is packaged by external forces or players in order to influence and individual's response to conduct or indeed behaviour. Salary is a good example of an extrinsic form of motivation which the hunger can be classified as an intrinsic motivation.

Some traders are motivated by intrinsic motivation that spurs growth of their businesses which others are indeed influenced by extrinsic factors. There are those motivated by a combination of both intrinsic and extrinsic factors or indeed other factors like religious beliefs of indeed the provision of basic services by government authorities. Such can be said to be motivated by **other factors** which are indeed outside the basic intrinsic or intrinsic factors and are also motivated by a hybrid combination of both intrinsic and extrinsic factors (which form a unique type of a factor that is indeed a hybrid of both intrinsic and extrinsic factors). Intrinsic motivational factors do include the following according to Thandukazi & Zondo, (2018), (i) Personal effort, (ii) Pursuit of new solutions to business problems, (iii) Need for recognition, (iv) Belief to produce desired outcomes, (v) Taking responsibility for business expansion, (vi) Need for advancement, (vii) Growth aspiration, (viii) Interest, (ix) involvement, (x) Satisfaction, (xi) Self-belief, (xii) Positive challenge, (xiii) Power needs, (xiv) Persistent effort to achieve results, (xv) Self-expression, and (xvi) Learning.

Self-determination, including self-development initiatives could be classified as intrinsic motivation, just like a sense of autonomy.

3.2. Extrinsic Motivation

Extrinsic motivation refers to forces or influences availed to an individual by other people. An individual with extrinsic motivation needs 'rewards' or facilities and incentives provided by other people in order to get motivated (Raini & Dessiana, 2019).

Rewards, salary, bonuses, promotion, facilities, provided by others, procedures, roads, loans, rules, future job prospects, money, reputation, peer recognition, visibility, gifts, financial incentives, status, penalties, benefits, power, fame, praise.

Other extrinsic factors include (1) Job security, (2) Good wages, (3) Promotion and growth, (4) Recognition, (5) Medals, (6) Discounts, and (7) A new uniform (Khan & Iqbal, 2013).

3.3. Extrinsic-Intrinsic relationships

Like has been said by Snelgar et al. (2017) there can be a thin line between intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation especially where the latter is being pursued in order to satisfy the former. An example is where one

works so hard in order to earn some money to buy food. It can therefore be argued about whether the individual is motivated by the anticipated monetary reward or the food that has to be bought to quench the hunger.

Money alone, cannot be the best motivator and can lead to frustration if organisational goals remain elusive or are never achieved (Snelgar et al., 2017).

Yet the view of intrinsicity or extrinsicity can be individualistic and relative, from one person to another. Thus research on motivational factors should not be done in the absence of an individual perspective which at time may affect research results. However, despite supporting the interplay of intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors. Snelgar et al. (2017) do confess that one set of motivational factors can be dominant over the other. Snelgar et al. (2017) do support the prominence of extrinsic factors over intrinsic motivational factors, especially, for an employee while Thundukazi and Zondo (2008) support the converse (intrinsic factors being dominant over extrinsic factors. Extrinsic motivation, by itself can be likened to operant conditioning whereby the individual is driven by the pursuit of a reward. Both intrinsic motivational factors and extrinsic motivational factor are, indeed motivating, on individual but can help bring different results, either in the short term or long term (Khan & Iqbal, 2013). Extrinsic factors are good when motivating individuals in the short term but where long term motivation is required, it is both extrinsic factors and intrinsic factors that matter.

Every type of expected tangible reward made contingent on task performance can undermine intrinsic motivation. External rewards, threats, directives and competition can undermine intrinsic motivation as they begin to control individual purposes and behaviour. Thus an increase in extrinsic rewards can undermine or have a negative effect on intrinsic motivation (Gottfried et al 2017; Miao & Evans, 2012; Khan & Iqbal, 2013; Thompson, 2014; Raini & Dessiana, 2019), although other scholars do dismiss that notion like Roberts et al. (2006), cited in Hartman (2011). Going by the two factor theory, hygiene factors work as extrinsic motivational factors while motivators work as intrinsic motivational factors (Khan & Iqbal, 2013).

3.4. Hybrid motivation

Proponents like Krishnamurthy (2006) and Robert et al. (2006), cited in Hartman (2011) support of the **other motivational factors theory which** hold that what is needed are hybrid factors born out of a combination of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational forces and that these are the ones which are responsible or effective at motivating individuals to higher heights, and indeed the fact that intrinsic factors and extrinsic factors go hand-in-hand in influencing behaviour. The theory of a combination or an interplay of both intrinsic and extrinsic factors, as being cardinal for success, is also supported by (Snelgar et al., 2017).

So it can be seen that while Thundukazi and Zondo (2008) promote intrinsic motivational factors rather than extrinsic factors, for success, Hartman (2011) propagates a blend of both motivational factors as being key to success. According to Hitka and Sirotiakova (2011) Motivational forces which can be classified as hybrid or ‘other’ motivation includes;

1. Training of employees – training makes employees gain confidence and removes fear or uncertainty. This includes all other forms of educational activities like short courses, seminars, long-courses, coaching sessions, managerial courses, IT courses, marketing, business management, including even language courses.

2. Team building exercises and protocols - These ensure that workers are part of the team.
3. Value system of an organisation - The value systems orients employees or workers towards a desired and progressive course of action.
4. Blend of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation - A blend of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation can have unique effects and thus qualify to be classified as a stand-alone or unique yet hybrid form of motivation (e.g., honesty plus other progressive religious beliefs).
5. Delegation of duties to employees - Though this can be seen as extrinsic, it can be a source of hybrid motivation given that it does not fall under pure intrinsic motivation.
6. Change in internal communication - to that which allows employees to become more open and candid to express themselves on matters that are progressive to a business entity.
7. Flexible working hours - Can lead to reduced burn-out or stress and motivate workers into more production.
8. Highlighting organisational accomplishments, big or small.
9. The whole architecture of political, economic, environmental, social and legal factors that spur growth but are neither extrinsic or intrinsic.
10. Good sanitation, as well as absence of disease.
11. Low cost of doing business (such as lower taxes, fees and levies).
12. Zero corruption.
13. Social skills of trader to include good communication with neighbours and clients, and staff.

Závadský, Hitka and Potkány (2015), after a study did highlight that key motivational factors, for an organisation, were (1) success (2) recognition (3) personal growth. It can be seen that these are not purely intrinsic or purely extrinsic goals. This justifies the need for a blend of motivational factors as being key to the growth of a business concern.

Kanfer (1990) as well as Hoogenstrid (2019) support the need for a hybrid, or unified perspective in motivation. Management can use a mix of factors to motivate employees, meaning that a blend of factors, called hybrid factors, do influence employees (Mensah, 2013). Employees who hold a mix of motivations do record a much higher growth than those who hold one type (intrinsic only or extrinsic only) Hoogenstrid (2019). Entrepreneurs of the future show characteristic of having complex aspirations and complex profiles (Cherkaoui, 2022).

Hybrid motivations can be exemplified by;

- a) Working for a financial reward to go and buy food and sort out the hunger.
- b) Pursuing a profitable business but motivated by the need to raise enough money to sponsor oneself for further studies (Lee, 2017).

Government is better off working with hybrid motivated establishments, if social and economic progress is achieved (Le Grand & Roberts, 2021).

4.0. Methodology

Methodology implies the systems and procedures including method that are be employed to conduct the study as well as to analyse and interpret results. Thus the methodology section is concerned with discussing methods and tools that are be used to collect, process and analyse data.

This study is a correlative study of variables employing a mixed method approach. The correlation is between sales value and the type of motivation that a grocery owners upholds, or espouses. Key variables are intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and the proposed hybrid motivation called ‘other motivation’ The specific type of mixed methods be to employ cluster sampling for a given section of a market as well as simple random sampling, from within each cluster. Such methods ensure representativeness of the target population (Smith & Albaum, 2012).

A population (of 1,300 shops) is to be selected across Lusaka district, with a sample population of 297 shop owners (within and around markets as well as on locations less than hundred meters from the market perimeter, for such are also considered to be part of a market. Sample size represents 40% of the targeted shop population. The sample size and population size, at a 95% confidence level, were arrived at on the recommendations of a 95% confidence interval. (Severna, 1975, p294; Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

Figure 1: An outline of selected market around Lusaka district

Sources: (Google Maps, 2022; Lusaka City Council, 2022)

The sample sizes of markets were motivated by the thought of Gosh (2011) as cited in a dissertation by Phiri (2015) who stated, “If the population of the universe is homogeneous, a small size of the sample may suffice for the purpose. These thought are also reinforced by Sekeran (1975) who stated that a sample size of larger than thirty members and less than five hundred is appropriate for most research; and also that “were samples are to be broken into sub-samples or categories, a minimum size of 30 is necessary for purposes of research (Sekeran, 1975, p295)

Population specific sample target group characteristic: Shop owners - Sample key characteristics:

- (a) An exact representation of the population characteristics.
- (b) They are typical of the informal traders that need to be studied for the purpose of this research.
- (c) They form a critical mass of research participants who are always present in the markets and would not give problems of attrition.
- (d) Many of the grocery shop owners grapple with motivation and performance related motivation.

(e) It is possible to segregate between those successful and those not successful, for purposes of analysis, among this group of participants.

It is believed that the central place embodies the characteristics of the other subsidiary or lower level markets. The central market to be chosen is the market at the end of each road from the central

Population catchment: For purposes of this study, markets located at the end of, or in the close proximity of key Bus Stations, at the end of the main roads, that originate from central business district (in town) is chosen. These are places that are at the centres of at the centre of major zones in the district. The zones, are naturally defined by the spaces between the key roads. The key roads of Lusaka district are;

1. Great East road;
2. Great North road;
3. Chilumbulu road;
4. Old Mumbwa road;
5. Kafue road.

The specific selected markets for the purpose of the study (see figure 1, in the appendix of this proposal) are;

- a) Chilenje market;
- b) Chainda market;
- c) Kanyama main market;
- d) Chilenje market;
- e) Kafue main Market;
- f) Matero main market.

The small market at the origin of the roads is left out of the study for two reasons namely (a) it does not have the same economic profile of restaurants as those in the townships (b) It has insignificant number of target participants.

4.1. Sample distribution

#	Market code	Market name	Market Committee Registered Grocery shop owners	Sample size	Distribution numbers of sample elements		Percentage % sample elements	
					Male	Female	Male	Female
1	CHI	Chainda	187	52	34	18	65.4	34.6
2	KSQ	Kaunda Sq Stg 1	303	62	44	18	71	29

3	MTE	Kanyama	99	35	25	10	71	29
4	CHG	Chilenje	405	62	46	16	74	26
5	KBW	Kafue	157	51	33	18	65	35
6	MTR	Matero	149	35	21	14	60	40
		Total	1300	297				

The sample size is 297 shops in the six markets as shown above. The sample distribution is as described in the table 1 above. It can be seen from table 1 that the distribution of male participants in the sample frame is an average of 68 percent while that of female is the average of 32 percent, with slight varying increases or reductions around the average figure, in respective markets. A pilot count by the researcher shows that over 50% of grocery are above the youthful age (of 18 to 35 years) and are in their mid-forties. Above the working age of 55, there is one female grocery owner in every 10 groceries, according to a pilot by the researcher on three markets. Thus it is felt that most women fall off the business between the ages of 35 and forty-five.

4.2. Instruments

Instruments to be used in this study include a semi-structured questionnaire. Actualisation of the questionnaire is through mail-in questionnaire as well as a telephone interview. Research questions focused on variables under extrinsic values, intrinsic values and a hybrid of intrinsic with extrinsic motivations (see raw data summary).

Physical observation remains an indispensable method of verifying an updating questionnaire responses as well as augmenting questionnaire data. So input from observation, as recorded in a research book is made full use of in so far as it entails augmenting research data. However, where there is a conflict between participant entries on to the questionnaire, and information gathered through physical observation, the latter took take supreme. Online questionnaires could be used only in exceptional circumstances and in so far as doing so does not dilute the contents on the original hardcopy questionnaire. A semi-structured questionnaire gives room to a researcher to probe further questions and thought of the respondent, regarding the questions being posed and a topic of discussion. Where a Likert scale is used on the questionnaire it ranged from 0 (to imply strongly disagree or not true) to 4 (to imply strongly agree or absolutely true).

5.0. Study Results

Data analysis allows for interpretation of the processed data in order to confirm trends, establish a relationship of causality and indeed reject the null hypothesis (which is the key objective of any post-positivist research). Graphs are being used to analyse trends in data. These include histograms, frequency graphs, and line graphs where appropriate.

Response rate was at 82%, and Cronbach's reliability test shows the reliability of the data is 0.81. This means that the data is reliable, and consistent and thus fit to be published. Other' motivation is responsible for improved performance among informal traders. Thus Motivational packages which are a hybrid of both intrinsic and extrinsic factors are most likely to bring about positive growth among informal players. *Improved performance can be attributed to 'other-motivation' in the informal sector, from the targeted population studied.*

The following were the findings

- i. From figure 3.5, $r = +0.817294$. This implies a strong positive correlation between 'other' motivation and annual sales.
- ii. From figure 4.2, $r = -0.245326$. This depicts a negative correlation between extrinsic motivation and annual sales.
- iii. From figure 5.2, $r = 0.063737$. This implies an extremely weak positive correlation between intrinsic motivation and annual sales.
- iv. The fact that majority of respondents hold or espouse intrinsic motivation and also given that an above-zero figure was obtained, albeit in the one-hundredth decimal place, show that intrinsic motivation is a dominant form of motivation among grocery owners. Given that majority of businesses are standing or going concerns, means that intrinsic motivation is essential to sustain business, in harsh informal environments that characterise informal trade. This is consistent with studies done by Thandukazi and Zondo (2018), which highlighted intrinsic motivation as a dominant motivation among small and medium enterprises (SMEs).
- v. Highest mean annual sales were recorded among extrinsically motivated traders, at K564003.80. This followed by those traders that espoused other motivation, with mean annual sales of K500644.70. This was followed by the mean of intrinsically motivated employees who posted means sales of K475579.6. Thus while intrinsic motivation is dominant. It cannot be tied to high mean annual sales supporting the fact that intrinsic motivation does well in holding traders in business, or sustaining businesses, rather than bring about improved sales, or performance.

6.0. Conclusion

Other' motivation is responsible for improved performance among informal traders. Thus Motivational packages which are a hybrid of both intrinsic and extrinsic factors are most likely to bring about positive growth among informal players. *Improved performance can be attributed to 'other-motivation' in the informal sector, from the targeted population studied.*

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7.0. Recommendation

Thus government authorities ought to design motivational strategies that are a blend of both intrinsic and extrinsic forces in order to bring about growth of informal sector businesses. This growth ultimately reduces the proliferation of informal businesses as growing businesses will graduate to become formal trade or formal concerns that ultimately contribute meaningfully to national Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

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Declarations

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare the total absence of conflicts of interest, both during the conduct of the study and during the written drafting of this work.

Consent for Publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Authors' Contributions

All the authors took part in literature review, analysis, and manuscript writing.

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Appendix

Table3: Other-motivational versus annual sales

Other Motiv level	Annual Sales
X	Y
33	950000
33	1152000
14	180000
20	288000
14	187200
15	573678
12	186708
27	625274
9	31920
15	831658

Source: Primary data

Figure 3.1: Other motivational levels versus annual sales

Source: Table 3

Figure 3.2: Line graph - Other motivation versus annual sales

Source: Table 3

Figure 3.3 Line of best fit - Other motivation versus sales

Source: Table 3

Figure 3.4: Other motivation and sales - Descriptive statistics

OTHER' MOTIVATION DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS			
X		Y	
Mean	19.2	Mean	500644.7
Standard Error	2.764055	Standard Error	121159.2
Median	15	Median	430843.5
Mode	14	Mode	#N/A
Standard Deviation	8.740709	Standard Deviation	383138.9
Sample Variance	76.4	Sample Variance	1.47E+11
Kurtosis	-0.90549	Kurtosis	-1.16611
Skewness	0.804344	Skewness	0.489881
Range	24	Range	1120080
Minimum	9	Minimum	31920
Maximum	33	Maximum	1152000
Sum	192	Sum	5006447
Count	10	Count	10

Mean K500644.7

Source: Table 3

Figure 3.5 : Correlation summary - 'other'' motivations with annual sales

	X	Y
X	1	
Y	0.817294	1

Source: Table 3

Figure 4.1: Extrinsic motivation summary statistics

X		Y	
Mean	4.125	Mean	564003.75
Standard Error	0.989904	Standard Error	56212.22506
Median	4	Median	547880
Mode	1	Mode	547880
Standard Deviation	2.799872	Standard Deviation	158992.1821
Sample Variance	7.839286	Sample Variance	25278513966
Kurtosis	-1.20304	Kurtosis	5.568239102
Skewness	0.402719	Skewness	2.194203785
Range	7	Range	515960
Minimum	1	Minimum	418890
Maximum	8	Maximum	934850
Sum	33	Sum	4512030
Count	8	Count	8
Confidence Interval @ 0.95	2.340752	Confidence Level	132920.7906
Mean annual Sales K564003.75			

Source: Table 4

Figure 4.2: Correlation summary: Extrinsic motivation versus annual sales

	X	Y
X	1	
Y	-0.24526	1

Source: Table 4

Figure 4.3: Extrinsic motivation versus annual sales

Source: Table 4

Figure 4.4: Line of best fit - Extrinsic motivation versus annual sales

Source: Table 4

Figure 5.1: Intrinsic motivation descriptive statistics

X		Y	
Mean	17.96889	Mean	475579.6
Standard Error	0.53724	Standard Error	16480.76
Median	18	Median	470486
Mode	12	Mode	547880
Standard Deviation	8.058597	Standard Deviation	247211.4
Sample Variance	64.94099	Sample Variance	6.11E+10
Kurtosis	-0.3085	Kurtosis	-0.38637
Skewness	0.183851	Skewness	-0.03585
Range	42	Range	1352262
Minimum	2	Minimum	-200262
Maximum	44	Maximum	1152000
Sum	4043	Sum	1.07E+08
Count	225	Count	225

Mean annual sales was 475579.6

Source: Table 5

Figure 5.2: Correlation summary Intrinsic motivation versus annual sales

	X	Y
X	1	
Y	0.063737	1

Source: Table 5

Table 2. Responses

#	Market code	Market name	Counted Pop. size	Sample size	Responded	% Responded
1	CHI	Chainda	187	52	35	67.31%
2	KSQ	Kaunda Sq Stg 1	303	62	56	90.32%
3	MTE	Kanyama	99	35	35	100.00%
4	CHG	Chilenje	405	62	47	78.33%
5	KBW	Kafue	157	51	40	78.43%
6	MTR	Matero	149	35	34	97.14%
		Total	1300	297	247	82.15%

Source: Primary data

Figure 6: Computation of Cronbach's alpha for data reliability

Source: Primary data

Excel Screenshots of pages of data and question response weighting

